

CHARACTERISTICS AND DEFINITION OF LEXICAL COMPETENCE

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Abstract. *In this article concepts of characteristics and definition of lexical competence, methodology of teaching lexical competences for multi-level learners with the help of computer technologies.*

Keywords: *Lexical competence, multi-level learners, computer technologies.*

ХАРАКТЕРИСТИКА И ОПРЕДЕЛЕНИЕ ЛЕКСИЧЕСКОЙ КОМПЕТЕНЦИИ

Аннотация. *В статье представлены понятия характеристики и определения лексической компетенции, методика обучения лексическим компетенциям многоуровневых учащихся с помощью компьютерных технологий.*

Ключевые слова: *Лексическая компетентность, многоуровневое обучение, компьютерные технологии.*

During the last decade or so more and more philosophers, linguists, psychologists, and computer scientists have become convinced that no complete account of our competence in the domain of word meaning can be given without a link between language and perception. Moreover, it has been claimed that the boundary between lexical and encyclopaedic knowledge is not clear cut (or may be completely absent): the way we use, perceive and conceptualise objects is part of a kind of knowledge that not only belongs to our lexical competence, but is precisely what allows us to know the meanings of words and to use them correctly.

It seemed to me that to be able to use a word is, on the one hand, to have access to a network of connections between that word and other words and linguistic expressions: it is to know that cats are animals, that in order to arrive somewhere one has to move, that an illness is something one may be cured of, and so forth. On the other hand, to be able to use a word is to know how to map lexical items onto the real world, that is, to be capable of both naming (selecting the right word in response to a given object or circumstance) and application (selecting the right object or circumstances in response to a given word). The two abilities are, to a large extent, independent of each other. The former ability can be called inferential, for it underlies our inferential performance (such as, for example, interpreting a general regulation concerning animals as applying to cats); the latter may be called referential.

I later discovered, thanks to Glyn Humphreys and other neuro-psychologists, that empirical research on brain-injured persons confirmed, to some extent, the intuitive picture of lexical competence I had been sketching. Inferential and referential abilities appeared to be separate.

Our second set of research directions concerns the inter-relationships between or across the aforementioned micro-, meso-, and exo-levels. Several researchers have examined the importance of cross level studies to examine how two or more levels interact and contradict/complement each other. Many of the extant studies do not explicitly adopt the TPACK lens. However, we provide these examples to highlight how TPACK can provide a deeper understanding of ICT integration. At the micro-level, the study evaluated how this ICT tool was usable for the teachers and students. At the meso-level, the study examined how the tool affected learning related to the school context. Next, the study described how this tool integrated with the museum, bridging the museum-classroom gap. This in essence is the exo-level. The study found that the tool could help extend the museum artifacts into the classroom context. The teacher's TPACK of designing the pre- and post-museum visits was important in helping the learners appreciate the experience and learn with the technology which explains how the "development and dissemination of professional knowledge as it relates to teaching and learning that incorporates information and communications technology" (p. 426) evolved and eventually transformed a community. Using the micro-, meso-, and macro-levels, the paper describes how the InterActive Education project has developed teachers' professional knowledge, and transformed the respective schools and their wider communities.

The study emphasized the meso-context of a knowledge-building teacher network where these teachers would design and implement technological innovation projects. In addition, Zhang) examines the interaction between the macro- and micro-levels in an East Asian learning culture. Macro-level elements are social values and power structures. Micro-level elements include resources and technologies, curriculum guidelines, assessment of learning, and learning tasks, activities and procedures. The author argues that ICT integration requires a principle-based rather than a procedure-based approach. This will engage teachers and allow them to deeply innovate with ICT.

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